

Mixed Least Squares–Total Least Squares from a Bayesian Perspective

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Abstract—Real-time estimation of partial error-in-variables (EIV) models is formulated within a Bayesian framework. The underlying regression-type stochastic model accounts for inaccurate measurements in selected regressor components corrupted by additive normal noise. Since existing partial EIV solvers are often computationally demanding and provide only point estimates, we derive a marginal output density and project the resulting posterior kernel onto the normal–Wishart distribution using a fixed-form variational approximation. The optimized posterior mean recovers the mixed least-squares–total-least-squares (LS–TLS) estimate and relates it to the maximum-likelihood (ML) solution. The paper also derives the exact Student’s t marginal posterior of the regression coefficients, establishes Fisher consistency of the Rayleigh-like mixed LS–TLS criterion, and contrasts its population target with that of ordinary LS, which is biased in the partial EIV setting.

I. INTRODUCTION

Measurement noise is ubiquitous in empirical data and may distort inference if ignored. In overdetermined systems, ordinary least squares (LS) assumes perturbations only in the right-hand side, whereas total least squares (TLS) applies when errors affect both the regressor matrix and the output vector. In the terminology of system identification, LS yields the standard solution for equation-error models [1], with TLS playing the analogous role for error-in-variables (EIV) models [2]. An important intermediate extension is the mixed LS–TLS formulation, which accommodates partial EIV models by allowing perturbations only in a designated subset of columns of the regressor matrix while treating the remaining columns as exact.

Both LS and TLS admit maximum-likelihood (ML) interpretations [3], the latter being linked to the minimization of a Rayleigh-quotient-like criterion. Iterative procedures such as the expectation-maximization algorithm [4] or quasi-linear LS [5] provide alternatives in the ML framework, monotonically increasing the likelihood and typically converging to a stationary point. Frequentist uncertainty analysis under the assumed EIV model is usually based on estimator covariance, confidence bounds, and the Cramér–Rao lower bound obtained from the inverse Fisher information matrix

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[4], [6]. Another major line of EIV identification uses bias-compensated LS techniques to recover the underlying noise-free input–output relationship; see Söderström’s survey [7].

By contrast, Bayesian treatments of TLS remain sparse compared with Bayesian LS methods [8]. This relative scarcity mainly reflects a broader challenge in Bayesian EIV inference: noisy inputs and outputs make the corresponding true variables latent. As a consequence, EIV models remain only weakly connected to the full Bayesian inferential machinery, including uncertainty quantification, model comparison, and decision-theoretic procedures [9].

Despite their relevance, partial EIV models have received only limited attention in the literature, and the available approaches rely predominantly on computationally nontrivial estimation procedures, ranging from sequential eigenpair-based identification algorithms [10] and nonlinear adjustment-based partial-EIV formulations [11], [12] to weighting-based iterative mixed LS–TLS solvers [13]. Although these approaches provide established numerical routes to mixed LS–TLS estimation, they remain data-matrix-based rather than being formulated as a recursive compression of the data stream into fixed-dimensional statistics. This paper addresses this gap by deriving a recursive mixed LS–TLS solution via an algebraic connection to LS, leading to a fixed-dimensional eigenvalue problem independent of the data length, and by embedding the resulting estimator into a Bayesian framework.

Notation: For a symmetric matrix $X \in \mathbb{R}^{n \times n}$, $\text{vech}(X)$ denotes the $\frac{1}{2}n(n+1) \times 1$ vector formed by stacking the elements on and below the main diagonal; $\text{vec}(X)$ is the $n^2 \times 1$ column-wise vectorization of X ; the zero-one duplication matrix $D_n \in \mathbb{R}^{n^2 \times \frac{1}{2}n(n+1)}$ is defined by $D_n \text{vech}(X) = \text{vec}(X)$; $\text{tr}(X)$ denotes its trace, $|X| = |\det(X)|$, and $X \succ 0$ indicates positive definiteness. Further, $O_{n,m}$ stands for the $n \times m$ zero matrix; I_n for the identity matrix of order n ; \otimes for the Kronecker product; x' for the transpose of x ; $\|x\|_2$ for the Euclidean norm of a vector x , i.e., $\|x\|_2 = (x'x)^{1/2}$; x^* for the range of x ; and \hat{x} is reserved either for the cardinality of a countable set x^* or for the dimension of a vector x . Throughout the paper, $f(x)$ denotes the probability density function (PDF) of a random variable x , with subscripts added whenever needed for distinction; the symbol \propto indicates equality up to a normalizing factor; \equiv signifies equality by definition; and $\mathcal{E}_{f(x)}[g(x)] = \int_{x^*} g(x)f(x) dx$ denotes the expectation of $g(x)$ with respect to $f(x)$.

II. DESIGNING THE ALGORITHM

Building on the algebraic connection between TLS and deregularized LS established in [14], we extend this perspec-

tive to the mixed LS-TLS setting. Section II-A recalls the Bayesian LS recursion, which accumulates data generated by a normal linear model into normal-Wishart (\mathcal{NW}) posterior statistics. The main contribution is developed in Section II-B, where the marginal output density of the partial EIV model is formulated, the optimal fixed-form variational \mathcal{NW} approximation to the exact posterior is derived, and the relation of the resulting estimate to the maximum-likelihood (ML) solution is clarified. The section also derives the exact Student's t (\mathcal{T}) marginal posterior and contrasts the population targets of the Rayleigh-like and ordinary LS criteria.

A. Ordinary LS from the Bayesian viewpoint

To compress the data into the LS statistics, consider the normal linear model

$$y_k = h'_k \theta + e_k, \quad e_k \sim \mathcal{N}(0, 1/d), \quad (1)$$

where $y_k \in \mathbb{R}$ is the measured output, $h_k \in \mathbb{R}^{\hat{\theta}}$ is a known deterministic regressor, $\theta \in \mathbb{R}^{\hat{\theta}}$ stacks the regression coefficients, and $d \in \mathbb{R}_{>0}$ is the unknown precision of the white normal noise. The samples are collected at instants $k \in k^* \equiv \{k_0, k_0 + 1, \dots, k_0 + \hat{k} - 1\} \subset \mathbb{Z}$. Casting (1) as a mapping from e_k to y_k yields

$$f(y_k | h_k, \theta, d) = \mathcal{N}(y_k | h'_k \theta, 1/d) \times \exp[-[\theta' \ 1] \psi_k \psi'_k [\theta' \ 1]' d/2], \quad (2)$$

where $\psi'_k \equiv [h'_k - y_k]$. Accumulating the models (2) over the available samples yields the likelihood $\prod_{i=1}^k f(y_i | h_i, \theta, d) = (2\pi/d)^{-k/2} \exp[-[\theta' \ 1] (\sum_{i=1}^k \psi_i \psi'_i) [\theta' \ 1]' d/2]$, whose exponent is a quadratic form in the augmented vector $[\theta' \ 1]'$. This functional form is preserved under multiplication by a normal-Wishart (\mathcal{NW}) prior and therefore yields a posterior belonging to the same family, namely

$$f(\theta, d | \mathcal{S}_k) \propto d^{(\nu_{ls;k} + \hat{\theta} - 2)/2} \exp\left[-\frac{d}{2} \begin{bmatrix} \theta \\ 1 \end{bmatrix}' \bar{V}_k \begin{bmatrix} \theta \\ 1 \end{bmatrix}\right]. \quad (3)$$

The corresponding augmented information matrix, partitioned according to the augmented vector $[\theta' \ 1]'$, is

$$\bar{V}_k = \begin{bmatrix} P_{ls;k}^{-1} & -P_{ls;k}^{-1} \hat{\theta}_{ls;k} \\ -\hat{\theta}'_{ls;k} P_{ls;k}^{-1} & \Sigma_{ls;k} + \hat{\theta}'_{ls;k} P_{ls;k}^{-1} \hat{\theta}_{ls;k} \end{bmatrix} \quad (4)$$

and \mathcal{S}_k collects the finite-dimensional statistics parameterizing the posterior, $\mathcal{S}_k \equiv \{\hat{\theta}_{ls;k}, P_{ls;k}, \Sigma_{ls;k}, \nu_{ls;k}\}$, where the subscript ls indicates quantities produced by the LS data update; under this \mathcal{NW} parametrization, $\Sigma_{ls;k} > 0$ and $\nu_{ls;k} > 2$ denote the accumulated least-squares remainder and the degrees-of-freedom parameter, respectively, with $\nu_{ls;k}$ increasing by one for each processed data sample. Equivalently, the posterior (3) factorizes into its conditional normal and marginal Wishart parts:

$$f(\theta | \mathcal{S}_k, d) = \mathcal{N}(\theta | \hat{\theta}_{ls;k}, P_{ls;k}/d) \times \exp[-(\theta - \hat{\theta}_{ls;k})' P_{ls;k}^{-1} (\theta - \hat{\theta}_{ls;k}) d/2], \quad (5)$$

$$f(d | \mathcal{S}_k) = \mathcal{W}(d | \Sigma_{ls;k}, \nu_{ls;k}) \times d^{(\nu_{ls;k} - 2)/2} \exp[-\Sigma_{ls;k} d/2]. \quad (6)$$

The factorization identifies, conditional on d , $\hat{\theta}_{ls;k}$ and $P_{ls;k}/d$ as the posterior mean and covariance of θ , while $\Sigma_{ls;k}$ and $\nu_{ls;k}$ parameterize the posterior PDF of d , with mean $\nu_{ls;k}/\Sigma_{ls;k}$.

Consequently, inference about $\{\theta, d\}$ proceeds recursively through updates of \mathcal{S}_k . To initialize the recursion, we adopt the following externally supplied PDF:

$$f(\theta, d | \hat{\theta}_{ls;k-1}, \Xi, \Sigma_{ls;0}, \nu_{ls;0}) \equiv \mathcal{N}(\theta | \hat{\theta}_{ls;k-1}, \Xi^{-1}/d) \times \mathcal{W}(d | \Sigma_{ls;0}, \nu_{ls;0}), \quad (7)$$

where Ξ is a positive-definite matrix controlling the regularization imposed on the estimate of θ . Given (7), the Bayesian update regularizes the parameter trajectory around the most recent estimate $\hat{\theta}_{ls;k-1}$ rather than the initial guess $\hat{\theta}_{ls;0}$.

By Bayes' rule, combining the data update with the time-varying regularization yields the functional recursion

$$f(\theta, d | \mathcal{S}_k) \propto \mathcal{N}(y_k | h'_k \theta, 1/d) \frac{\mathcal{N}(\theta | \hat{\theta}_{ls;k-1}, \Xi^{-1}/d)}{\mathcal{N}(\theta | \hat{\theta}_{ls;k-2}, \Xi^{-1}/d)} \times \mathcal{N}(\theta | \hat{\theta}_{ls;k-1}, P_{ls;k-1}/d) \mathcal{W}(d | \Sigma_{ls;k-1}, \nu_{ls;k-1}). \quad (8)$$

At $k = 1$, the same user-specified initial estimate is used for both $\hat{\theta}_{ls;-1}$ and $\hat{\theta}_{ls;0}$, while the initial normalized (by d) covariance is set as $P_{ls;0} \equiv \Xi^{-1}$, so that (7) formally serves as the prior PDF. Owing to the conjugacy of the PDFs on the right-hand side of (8), the functional recursion collapses to the following least-squares-like recursion:

$$\varepsilon_{k-1} \equiv \hat{\theta}_{ls;k-1} - \hat{\theta}_{ls;k-2}, \quad (9)$$

$$\hat{\theta}_{c;k-1} \equiv \hat{\theta}_{ls;k-1} + P_{ls;k-1} \Xi \varepsilon_{k-1}, \quad (10)$$

$$\Sigma_{c;k-1} \equiv \Sigma_{ls;k-1} - \varepsilon'_{k-1} (I_{\hat{\theta}} + \Xi P_{ls;k-1}) \Xi \varepsilon_{k-1}, \quad (11)$$

$$K_k \equiv P_{ls;k-1} h_k / (1 + h'_k P_{ls;k-1} h_k), \quad (12)$$

$$\hat{e}_k \equiv y_k - h'_k \hat{\theta}_{c;k-1}, \quad (13)$$

$$\hat{\theta}_{ls;k} \equiv \hat{\theta}_{c;k-1} + K_k \hat{e}_k, \quad (14)$$

$$P_{ls;k} \equiv (I_{\hat{\theta}} - K_k h'_k) P_{ls;k-1} (I_{\hat{\theta}} - K_k h'_k)' + K_k K'_k, \quad (15)$$

$$V_{ls;k} \equiv P_{ls;k}^{-1} = V_{ls;k-1} + h_k h'_k, \quad (16)$$

$$\Sigma_{ls;k} \equiv \Sigma_{c;k-1} + \hat{e}_k^2 / (1 + h'_k P_{ls;k-1} h_k), \quad (17)$$

$$\nu_{ls;k} \equiv \nu_{ls;k-1} + 1. \quad (18)$$

Next, LS is modified for a partial EIV setting by accounting for uncertainty in selected entries of the regressor vector.

B. Mixed LS-TLS from the Bayesian viewpoint

We consider a partial EIV model with the regressor partitioned as $h_k \equiv [h'_{u;k} \ h'_{y;k}]'$, where $h_{u;k}$ is observed without error and $h_{y;k}$ is noise-corrupted. Accordingly, the parameter vector is split into $\theta \equiv [\theta'_u \ \theta'_y]'$, and the model is written as

$$\begin{cases} h_{y;k} = h_{y_0;k} + \xi_k, & \xi_k \sim \mathcal{N}(O_{\hat{\theta}_y,1}, I_{\hat{\theta}_y}/d), \\ y_k = \underbrace{[h'_{u;k} \ h'_{y_0;k}]}_{y_{0;k}} \theta + e_k, & e_k \sim \mathcal{N}(0, 1/d), \end{cases} \quad (19)$$

where $h_{y_0;k} \in \mathbb{R}^{\hat{\theta}_y}$ denotes the latent noise-free counterpart of $h_{y;k}$. The sequences $\{e_k\}$ and $\{\xi_k\}$ are assumed to be

temporally white and mutually uncorrelated, with $\{\xi_k\}$ also spatially white.

To specify the parametric model, we construct the joint PDF of y_k and the latent component $h_{y_0;k}$, conditional on θ , d , and h_k . This joint PDF follows from the affine change of variables from $[e_k \xi_k']'$ to $[y_k h'_{y_0;k}]'$, induced by

$$\left| \frac{\partial}{\partial \begin{bmatrix} y_k \\ h_{y_0;k} \end{bmatrix}'} \left(\underbrace{\begin{bmatrix} 1 & -\theta'_y \\ O_{\hat{\theta}_y,1} & -I_{\hat{\theta}_y} \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} y_k \\ h_{y_0;k} \end{bmatrix} + \begin{bmatrix} -h'_{u;k} \theta_u \\ h_{y;k} \end{bmatrix}}_{\mathcal{X}} \right) \right| \times \mathcal{N} \left(\mathcal{X} | O_{\hat{\theta}_y+1,1}, I_{\hat{\theta}_y+1} / d \right).$$

Consequently, the joint PDF takes the form

$$f \left(\begin{bmatrix} y_k \\ h_{y_0;k} \end{bmatrix} \middle| \theta, d, h_k \right) = \mathcal{N} \left(\begin{bmatrix} y_k \\ h_{y_0;k} \end{bmatrix} \middle| \begin{bmatrix} h'_k \theta \\ h_{y;k} \end{bmatrix}, \frac{1}{d} \begin{bmatrix} 1 + \theta'_y \theta_y & \theta'_y \\ \theta_y & I_{\hat{\theta}_y} \end{bmatrix} \right). \quad (20)$$

Since only $f(y_k | \theta, d, h_k)$ enters the posterior update, the nuisance component $h_{y_0;k}$ is marginalized out of the joint PDF in (20). Using the marginal–conditional factorization $f(y_k, h_{y_0;k} | \theta, d, h_k) = f(y_k | \theta, d, h_k) f(h_{y_0;k} | y_k, \theta, d, h_k)$ (Claim 1 in [15]), the marginal PDF of interest is given by

$$f(y_k | \theta, d, h_k) = \mathcal{N}(y_k | h'_k \theta, 1/(d\omega^2)), \quad (21)$$

where $\omega^2 \equiv 1/(1 + \theta' S' S \theta)$. Here, $S \equiv [O_{\hat{\theta}_y, \hat{\theta}_u} I_{\hat{\theta}_y}]$ is a selection matrix satisfying $\theta_y = S \theta$.

To preserve the normal–Wishart-like functional form induced by the parametric model (21), we choose the externally supplied PDF, conditional on ω , to be

$$f(\theta, d | \hat{\theta}_{ls;k-1}, \Xi, \Sigma_{ls;0}, \nu_{ls;0}, \omega) = \mathcal{N}(\theta | \hat{\theta}_{ls;k-1}, \Xi^{-1}/(d\omega^2)) \mathcal{W}(d | \Sigma_{ls;0} \omega^2, \nu_{ls;0}). \quad (22)$$

Upon combining this prior with the sequentially acquired data, the posterior becomes

$$f(\theta, d | \mathcal{S}_k, \omega) \propto \mathcal{N}(y_k | h'_k \theta, 1/(d\omega^2)) (d\omega^2)^{(\nu_{ls;k-1} + \hat{\theta})/2} \times \frac{1}{d} \exp \left[-\frac{d\omega^2}{2} \begin{bmatrix} \theta \\ 1 \end{bmatrix}' \begin{bmatrix} P_{ls;k-1}^{-1} & \mathcal{M}'_{21} \\ \mathcal{M}_{21} & \mathcal{M}_{22} \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} \theta \\ 1 \end{bmatrix} \right], \quad (23)$$

where $\mathcal{M}_{21} \equiv -\hat{\theta}'_{c;k-1} P_{ls;k-1}^{-1}$ and $\mathcal{M}_{22} \equiv \Sigma_{c;k-1} + \hat{\theta}'_{c;k-1} P_{ls;k-1}^{-1} \hat{\theta}_{c;k-1}$.

The adopted variational design introduces the trial $\mathcal{N}\mathcal{W}$ density, $f_t \equiv \mathcal{N}(\theta | \hat{\theta}_k, P_k/d) \mathcal{W}(d | \Sigma_k, \nu_k)$, to fit the exact posterior f_e , defined up to a normalizing factor by the right-hand side of (23),

$$f_e \propto \mathcal{N}(y_k | h'_k \theta, 1/(d\omega^2)) \mathcal{N}(\theta | \hat{\theta}_{c;k-1}, P_{ls;k-1}/(d\omega^2)) \times \mathcal{W}(d | \Sigma_{c;k-1} \omega^2, \nu_{ls;k-1}).$$

The approximation is constructed subject to the constraint $\omega^2 \equiv 1/(1 + \theta' S' S \theta)$, yielding a mass-concentrating approximation centered in a high-posterior-density region. The resulting variational posterior recovers the mixed LS–TLS

estimate as the posterior mean of θ and quantifies the associated uncertainty through credible regions. To this end, the discrepancy is quantified by the Kullback–Leibler divergence (KLD) [16] from $f_t(\theta, d)$ to $f_e(\theta, d)$:

$$\mathcal{D}(f_t || f_e) \equiv \int_{\theta^*} \int_{d^*} f_t(\theta, d) \ln \left(\frac{f_t(\theta, d)}{f_e(\theta, d)} \right) d\theta dd.$$

By construction, $\mathcal{D}(f_t || f_e) \geq 0$, and it vanishes if and only if the trial density matches the exact posterior (almost everywhere), i.e., $f_t = f_e$. Building on the foregoing discussion, we introduce a loss function that quantifies the discrepancy arising when f_t is used to emulate the data-update process (23). To optimize the statistics of f_t , we adopt

$$\mathcal{L}(\hat{\theta}_k, P_k, \Sigma_k, \nu_k, \omega) \equiv \mathcal{D}(f_t || \omega^{-\nu_{ls;k}} f_e) - \frac{\eta}{2} \int_{\mathbb{R}^{\hat{\theta}}} \int_0^\infty d(\omega^2(\theta'_y \theta_y + 1 - \text{tr}(SP_k S')/d) - 1) f_t d\theta dd. \quad (24)$$

The η -scaled term in (24) is included to enforce a hard equality constraint on the posterior mean. The constraint is normalized by d so that its scaling matches the quadratic terms in the exponentials of the participating PDFs. Moreover, the Wishart part is treated via an unnormalized relaxation, $\omega^{-\nu_{ls;k}} f_e$; otherwise, the Lagrange-multiplier formulation becomes degenerate and fails to identify the extrema. The loss function (24) is evaluated by rewriting it as a sum of expectations under the trial PDF f_t , which reduce to standard integrals involving the gamma $\Gamma(\cdot)$ and digamma $\Psi(\cdot)$ functions. In particular, we use the logarithmic-moment identity [17] given by $\mathcal{E}_{\mathcal{W}(d | \Sigma_k, \nu_k)}[\ln(d)] = \Psi(\nu_k/2) + \ln(2) - \ln(\Sigma_k)$ to evaluate the expected logarithmic terms in (24):

$$\begin{aligned} & \mathcal{E}_{\mathcal{N}(\theta | \hat{\theta}_k, P_k/d) \mathcal{W}(d | \Sigma_k, \nu_k)} \left[\ln(\mathcal{W}(d | \Sigma_{c;k-1} \omega^2, \nu_{ls;k-1})) \right] \\ & \times \mathcal{N}(\theta | \hat{\theta}_{c;k-1}, P_{ls;k-1}/(d\omega^2)) = (\hat{\theta} + \nu_{ls;k-1}) \ln(\omega) \\ & + \ln \left((2\pi)^{-\frac{\hat{\theta}}{2}} |V_{ls;k-1}|^{\frac{1}{2}} \left(\frac{\Sigma_{c;k-1}}{2} \right)^{\frac{\nu_{ls;k-1}}{2}} \frac{1}{\Gamma(\frac{\nu_{ls;k-1}}{2})} \right) \\ & + \frac{\nu_{ls;k-1} + \hat{\theta} - 2}{2} \left[\Psi \left(\frac{\nu_k}{2} \right) + \ln \left(\frac{2}{\Sigma_k} \right) \right] \\ & - \frac{\omega^2}{2} (\hat{\theta}_k - \hat{\theta}_{c;k-1})' V_{ls;k-1} (\hat{\theta}_k - \hat{\theta}_{c;k-1}) \frac{\nu_k}{\Sigma_k} \\ & - \frac{\omega^2}{2} \left(\frac{\Sigma_{c;k-1} \nu_k}{\Sigma_k} + \text{tr}(P_k V_{ls;k-1}) \right). \end{aligned}$$

With these closed-form templates in place, the final expres-

sion of (24) is given by

$$\begin{aligned}
& \mathcal{L}(\hat{\theta}_k, P_k, \Sigma_k, \nu_k, \omega) \\
&= \frac{1}{2} \ln \left(\frac{|P_k|^{-1}}{|V_{ls;k}|} \right) + \frac{\omega^2}{2} \text{tr}(V_{ls;k} P_k) + \ln \left(\frac{\Gamma(\nu_{ls;k}/2)}{\Gamma(\nu_k/2)} \right) \\
&\quad - \frac{\hat{\theta}}{2} + \frac{\nu_{ls;k}}{2} \ln \left(\frac{\Sigma_k}{\Sigma_{ls;k}} \right) - \frac{\nu_k}{2} \left(1 - \frac{\omega^2 \Sigma_{ls;k}}{\Sigma_k} \right) \\
&\quad + \frac{\nu_k \omega^2}{2 \Sigma_k} (\hat{\theta}_k - \hat{\theta}_{ls;k})' V_{ls;k} (\hat{\theta}_k - \hat{\theta}_{ls;k}) - \hat{\theta} \ln(\omega) \\
&\quad + \frac{\nu_k - \nu_{ls;k}}{2} \Psi \left(\frac{\nu_k}{2} \right) - \frac{\eta \nu_k}{2 \Sigma_k} (\omega^2 \hat{\theta}_k' S' S \hat{\theta}_k + \omega^2 - 1).
\end{aligned}$$

The lemma below shows that the mixed LS-TLS point estimate coincides with the variational posterior mean of θ obtained by projecting the exact posterior onto the \mathcal{NW} family via minimization of \mathcal{L} in (24).

Lemma 1: Let the trial PDF f_t approximate f_e , with f_t restricted to the \mathcal{NW} functional form. Then, the optimal \mathcal{NW} representative is obtained by minimizing the objective \mathcal{L} in (24), yielding

$$\hat{\theta}_{x;k} = (V_{ls;k} - \hat{\eta} S' S)^{-1} V_{ls;k} \hat{\theta}_{ls;k}, \quad (25)$$

$$\hat{\omega}_k^2 = 1/(\hat{\theta}_{x;k}' S' S \hat{\theta}_{x;k} + 1), \quad (26)$$

$$P_{x;k}^{-1} \equiv V_{x;k} = \hat{\omega}_k^2 V_{ls;k}, \quad (27)$$

$$\Sigma_{x;k} = \hat{\eta} \quad (28)$$

$$= \hat{\omega}_k^2 \Sigma_{ls;k} + \hat{\omega}_k^2 (\hat{\theta}_{x;k} - \hat{\theta}_{ls;k})' V_{ls;k} (\hat{\theta}_{x;k} - \hat{\theta}_{ls;k}),$$

$$\nu_{x;k} = \nu_{ls;k}, \quad (29)$$

where the subscript x refers to the optimized statistics of the trial PDF f_t , and the corresponding set $\{\hat{\theta}_{x;k}, P_{x;k}, \Sigma_{x;k}, \nu_{x;k}, \hat{\omega}_k^2\}$ constitutes the unique global minimizer of \mathcal{L} . The optimal Lagrange multiplier $\hat{\eta}$ equals the smallest eigenvalue of the symmetric matrix \mathcal{Z} defined below; the time index k is omitted for brevity:

$$\mathcal{Z} \equiv \begin{bmatrix} \underbrace{V_{ls,yy} - V_{ls,yu} V_{ls,uu}^{-1} V_{ls,yu}'}_{P_{ls,yy}^{-1}} & -P_{ls,yy}^{-1} \hat{\theta}_{ls,y} \\ -\hat{\theta}_{ls,y}' P_{ls,yy}^{-1} & \hat{\theta}_{ls,y}' P_{ls,yy}^{-1} \hat{\theta}_{ls,y} + \Sigma_{ls} \end{bmatrix}, \quad (30)$$

where $V_{ls,yy} \in \mathbb{R}^{\hat{\theta}_y \times \hat{\theta}_y}$, $V_{ls,yu} \in \mathbb{R}^{\hat{\theta}_y \times \hat{\theta}_u}$, and $V_{ls,uu} \in \mathbb{R}^{\hat{\theta}_u \times \hat{\theta}_u}$ are submatrices of the information matrix $V_{ls} \equiv \begin{bmatrix} V_{ls,uu} & V_{ls,yu}' \\ V_{ls,yu} & V_{ls,yy} \end{bmatrix}$, and $\hat{\theta}_{ls,y}$ is the subvector of the mean $\hat{\theta}_{ls} \equiv [\hat{\theta}_{ls,u} \ \hat{\theta}_{ls,y}]'$, partitioned conformably with $\theta = [\theta'_u \ \theta'_y]'$.

Proof: A proof of the unique global optimality of the solution is given in the Appendix via the first-order necessary and second-order sufficient optimality conditions. ■

When interest centers on the regression coefficients θ alone, the unknown precision variable d can be integrated out from the \mathcal{NW} posterior, yielding the marginal posterior

density of θ in the form of a multivariate \mathcal{T} distribution:

$$\begin{aligned}
& \int_0^\infty \mathcal{N}(\theta | \hat{\theta}_{x;k}, P_{x;k}/d) \mathcal{W}(d | \Sigma_{x;k}, \nu_{x;k}) dd \quad (31) \\
&= \mathcal{T}(\theta | \hat{\theta}_{x;k}, \Sigma_{x;k} P_{x;k}, \nu_{x;k}) \\
&\propto [1 + (\theta - \hat{\theta}_{x;k})' P_{x;k}^{-1} (\theta - \hat{\theta}_{x;k}) / \Sigma_{x;k}]^{-(\nu_{x;k} + \hat{\theta})/2}.
\end{aligned}$$

Within a maximum-likelihood (ML) treatment of the partial EIV problem, the joint ML estimator of θ and $\{h_{y_0;i}\}_{i=1}^k$ is defined as the solution to

$$\max_{\theta} \max_{\{h_{y_0;i}\}_{i=1}^k} \ln \prod_{i=1}^k f(y_i, h_{y_0;i} | \theta, d, h_i). \quad (32)$$

Here, the likelihood, evaluated at the observed data, is formed from the joint PDFs given in (20) and regarded as a function of θ and $\{h_{y_0;i}\}_{i=1}^k$. Under the normal assumption, the above problem is equivalent to

$$\begin{aligned}
\hat{\theta}_{x;k} &= \arg \min_{\theta} \min_{\{h_{y_0;i}\}_{i=1}^k} \left[\sum_{i=1}^k (y_i - y_{0;i})^2 \right. \\
&\quad \left. + \sum_{i=1}^k \|h_{y_0;i} - h_{y_0;i}\|_2^2 \right] = \arg \min_{\theta} \omega^2 \sum_{i=1}^k (y_i - h'_i \theta)^2. \quad (33)
\end{aligned}$$

In this way, the latent variables are eliminated by carrying out the inner minimization, thereby reducing the original problem to a weighted LS problem. Neglecting the effect of the prior information, its solution coincides with (25). The following proposition establishes the Fisher consistency of the Rayleigh-like criterion underlying (25).

Proposition 1: Consider the partial EIV model (19), where $h_{0;i} \equiv [h'_{u;i} \ h'_{y_0;i}]'$. Suppose that the measurement-error sequences $\{e_i\}_{i=1}^k$ and $\{\xi_i\}_{i=1}^k$ form zero-mean, mutually uncorrelated white-noise processes, independent of $\{h_{0;i}\}_{i=1}^k$, with $\mathcal{E}_{e_i}[e_i^2] = 1/d$ and $\mathcal{E}_{\xi_i}[\xi_i \xi_i'] = I_{\hat{\theta}_y}/d$. Let θ_0 denote the true value of the parameter vector, and define the Rayleigh-like criterion $J_k(\theta) \equiv \frac{\sum_{i=1}^k (y_i - h'_i \theta)^2}{1 + \theta' S' S \theta}$. If $R_0 \equiv \sum_{i=1}^k \mathcal{E}_{h_{0;i}}[h_{0;i} h'_{0;i}] \succ 0$, then $J_k(\theta)$ is Fisher-consistent in the population sense, so that the estimating rule $\hat{\theta}_{x;k} = \arg \min_{\theta} J_k(\theta)$ targets θ_0 at the population level.

Proof: The expected counterpart of $J_k(\theta)$ taken over $\{e_i, \xi_i, h_{0;i}\}_{i=1}^k$ satisfies $\mathcal{E}_{\{e_i, \xi_i, h_{0;i}\}_{i=1}^k} [J_k(\theta) | \theta_0] = \frac{k}{d} + \frac{(\theta - \theta_0)' R_0 (\theta - \theta_0)}{1 + \theta' S' S \theta}$. Since $R_0 \succ 0$, the second term is non-negative and vanishes only at $\theta = \theta_0$. Hence, the expected criterion is uniquely minimized at θ_0 . ■

Viewed from the Bayesian standpoint, integrating out the unknown precision d from the exact posterior PDF f_e gives $f(\theta | \mathcal{S}_k) = \int_0^\infty f_e dd$. To evaluate this integral analytically, it is convenient to invoke the factorization $f(\theta, d | \mathcal{S}_k) = f(\theta | \mathcal{S}_k) f(d | \mathcal{S}_k, \theta)$, under which the integrand is identified as proportional to the Wishart density kernel ϕ . This observation

yields

$$f(\theta|\mathcal{S}_k) \propto \omega^{(\nu_{ls;k} + \hat{\theta})} \quad (34)$$

$$\times \int_0^\infty \overbrace{d^{(\nu_{ls;k} + \hat{\theta} - 2)/2} \exp\left[-\frac{d\omega^2}{2} \begin{bmatrix} \theta \\ 1 \end{bmatrix}' \bar{V}_k \begin{bmatrix} \theta \\ 1 \end{bmatrix}\right]}^\phi dd$$

$$\propto [1 + (\theta - \hat{\theta}_{ls;k})' P_{ls;k}^{-1} (\theta - \hat{\theta}_{ls;k}) / \Sigma_{ls;k}]^{-(\nu_{ls;k} + \hat{\theta})/2},$$

where $\mathcal{W}(d|\omega^2[\frac{\theta}{1}]' \bar{V}_k [\frac{\theta}{1}], \nu_{ls;k} + \hat{\theta}) \propto \phi$, showing that the marginal posterior PDF of $\theta|\mathcal{S}_k$ follows a \mathcal{T} distribution, with its location and scale determined by the ordinary LS statistics. Nevertheless, in contrast to $J_k(\theta)$, the expected counterpart of the ordinary LS criterion $\mathcal{E}_{\{e_i, \xi_i, h_{0,i}\}_{i=1}^k} [\sum_{i=1}^k (y_i - h_i' \theta)^2 | \theta_0]$ is minimized at $(R_0 + \frac{k}{d} S' S)^{-1} R_0 \theta_0$, which generally differs from θ_0 ; hence, the ordinary LS criterion is not Fisher-consistent in the partial EIV setting.

III. ILLUSTRATIVE EXPERIMENTS

The theoretical developments are illustrated numerically on the partial EIV model (19),

$$v_{1;k} = v_{0,1;k} + \xi_{1;k}, \quad v_{2;k} = v_{0,2;k} + \xi_{2;k},$$

$$y_k = \theta_1 u_k + \theta_2 u_{k-1} + \theta_3 v_{0,1;k} + \theta_4 v_{0,2;k} + e_k,$$

where u_k is observed without error, while the available signals satisfy $y_k = y_{0;k} + e_k$ and $v_k = v_{0;k} + \xi_k$ ($v_k = [v_{1;k} \ v_{2;k}]'$). The measurement errors e_k , $\xi_{1;k}$, and $\xi_{2;k}$ are assumed to be normally distributed and mutually uncorrelated. The true parameter vector is set to $\theta_0 = [0.5 \ -0.5 \ 2 \ -2]'$. The regressor components are generated according to $[u_k \ v_{0,k}']' \sim \mathcal{N}(O_{3,1}, I_3)$. Further, the sequential learning process governed by the LS recursion (9)–(18) is initialized by the user-defined hyperparameters $\nu_{ls;0} = 10$, $\Xi = 10^{-3} I_4$, $\Sigma_{ls;0} = 1$, and $\hat{\theta}_{ls;0} = \hat{\theta}_{ls;-1} = O_{4,1}$.

The numerical study compares the exact posterior (34), hereafter denoted by \mathcal{T}_{ls} , with the \mathcal{T}_x posterior (31) associated with the variational approximation. For each configuration specified by the data length N and the noise precision d , a Monte Carlo experiment with $M = 1000$ independent runs is carried out. In the l th run ($l = 1, \dots, M$), a new dataset is generated from the model, and both posterior parameterizations are evaluated to obtain the corresponding estimates $\hat{\theta}_{z;N}^{(l)}$ together with the nominal 95% credible interval for each component of θ , whose lower and upper bounds are denoted by $\underline{\theta}_{z,i}^{(l)}$ and $\bar{\theta}_{z,i}^{(l)}$, respectively, where $z \in \{ls, x\}$. The estimation accuracy is quantified by the mean absolute relative error, $\text{MARE}_{z,i} \equiv \frac{100}{M} \sum_{l=1}^M \frac{|\hat{\theta}_{z,i}^{(l)} - \theta_{0,i}|}{|\theta_{0,i}|}$, whereas the quality of uncertainty quantification is assessed through the empirical coverage probability $\text{ECP}_{z,i} \equiv \frac{1}{M} \sum_{l=1}^M \mathbf{1}\{\theta_{0,i} \in [\underline{\theta}_{z,i}^{(l)}, \bar{\theta}_{z,i}^{(l)}]\}$, where $\mathbf{1}\{E\}$ denotes the indicator function taking value one if the event E occurs and zero otherwise, and through the mean interval length $\text{MIL}_{z,i} \equiv \frac{1}{M} \sum_{l=1}^M (\bar{\theta}_{z,i}^{(l)} - \underline{\theta}_{z,i}^{(l)})$.

Table I summarizes the Monte Carlo results, with bold entries indicating the lower componentwise $\text{MARE}_{z,i}$, the $\text{ECP}_{z,i}$ closest to the nominal 0.95 level, and, in the

last row, the lower component-averaged error $\text{AMARE}_z \equiv \hat{\theta}^{-1} \sum_{i=1}^{\hat{\theta}} \text{MARE}_{z,i}$. For $d = 100$, the two posterior constructions yield nearly identical estimation and uncertainty quantification performance. At $d = 10$, however, the main advantage of \mathcal{T}_x appears in θ_3 and θ_4 , i.e., the parameters associated with the error-contaminated regressor components, where it substantially lowers the MARE and brings the ECP much closer to the nominal level. This behavior is consistent with the population-level analysis: the mixed LS–TLS estimating rule underlying \mathcal{T}_x targets θ_0 , whereas the ordinary LS criterion associated with \mathcal{T}_{ls} has a biased population minimizer in the partial EIV setting. The improvement becomes more pronounced as the data length N increases, while the MIL values remain similar for both approaches, indicating that the improved coverage of \mathcal{T}_x is not obtained through substantially wider credible intervals.

IV. CONCLUSION

This paper provides a rigorous Bayesian interpretation of the mixed LS–TLS problem arising in partial EIV models. By incorporating uncertainty in the error-contaminated regressor components, the proposed formulation embeds mixed LS–TLS into an equality-constrained fixed-form variational Bayes problem, with the derivation rooted in optimization theory and carried out via the method of Lagrange multipliers. Grounded in the algebraic connection between ordinary LS and mixed LS–TLS estimation, the proposed construction yields a posterior distribution whose mean recovers the mixed LS–TLS estimate and whose spread quantifies uncertainty in the inferred parameters. The analysis further links the proposed variational approximation to the maximum-likelihood viewpoint via the Rayleigh-like criterion and shows that the resulting mixed LS–TLS rule is Fisher-consistent, unlike ordinary LS in the partial EIV setting. The paper also derives the exact marginal posterior, yielding a heavy-tailed Student's t distribution parameterized by LS statistics. The approximate and exact solutions can therefore be viewed as two distinct treatments of latent regressor elimination: extremization and marginalization.

APPENDIX

By imposing stationarity of the objective \mathcal{L} with respect to the design variables $\Theta = [\text{vech}(P_k)', \hat{\theta}_k', \omega, \Sigma_k, \nu_k]'$ and the multiplier η at $\hat{\Theta} = [\text{vech}(P_{x;k})', \hat{\theta}'_{x;k}, \hat{\omega}_k, \Sigma_{x;k}, \nu_{x;k}]'$ and $\hat{\eta}$, we arrive at the first-order necessary optimality conditions:

$$\frac{\partial \mathcal{L}}{\partial \text{vech}(P_k)} \Big|_{\hat{\Theta}} = -\frac{1}{2} D'_{\hat{\theta}} \text{vec}(V_{x;k}) + \frac{\hat{\omega}_k^2}{2} D'_{\hat{\theta}} \text{vec}(V_{ls;k})$$

$$= 0, \quad (A.1)$$

$$\frac{\partial \mathcal{L}}{\partial \hat{\theta}_k} \Big|_{\hat{\Theta}} = \hat{\omega}_k^2 \frac{\nu_{x;k}}{\Sigma_{x;k}} V_{ls;k} (\hat{\theta}_{x;k} - \hat{\theta}_{ls;k})$$

$$- \hat{\eta} \hat{\omega}_k^2 \frac{\nu_{x;k}}{\Sigma_{x;k}} S' S \hat{\theta}_{x;k} = 0, \quad (A.2)$$

$$\frac{\partial \mathcal{L}}{\partial \omega_k} \Big|_{\hat{\Theta}} = 0 \implies -\hat{\eta} (\hat{\omega}_k^2 \hat{\theta}'_{x;k} S' S \hat{\theta}_{x;k} + \hat{\omega}_k^2) + \Sigma_{x;k}$$

TABLE I. Monte Carlo comparison of the two Student's t posterior parameterizations for the partial EIV model.

Method	Metric	$N = 50, d = 100$				$N = 50, d = 10$				$N = 150, d = 100$				$N = 150, d = 10$			
		θ_1	θ_2	θ_3	θ_4	θ_1	θ_2	θ_3	θ_4	θ_1	θ_2	θ_3	θ_4	θ_1	θ_2	θ_3	θ_4
\mathcal{T}_{ls}	MARE [%]	7.348	7.263	1.941	2.006	22.248	22.001	9.587	9.700	3.999	4.032	1.281	1.345	12.228	12.269	8.980	9.149
\mathcal{T}_x	MARE [%]	7.395	7.323	1.817	1.884	23.459	23.336	5.877	6.066	4.008	4.051	1.018	1.057	12.718	12.828	3.302	3.446
\mathcal{T}_{ls}	ECP	0.936	0.945	0.915	0.901	0.889	0.921	0.654	0.601	0.938	0.951	0.876	0.851	0.934	0.930	0.280	0.260
\mathcal{T}_x	ECP	0.933	0.946	0.923	0.923	0.897	0.915	0.889	0.871	0.936	0.948	0.941	0.932	0.929	0.938	0.911	0.898
\mathcal{T}_{ls}	MIL	0.172	0.172	0.173	0.170	0.475	0.475	0.458	0.451	0.097	0.097	0.096	0.096	0.286	0.286	0.272	0.271
\mathcal{T}_x	MIL	0.173	0.173	0.174	0.171	0.498	0.497	0.479	0.472	0.098	0.098	0.097	0.097	0.299	0.299	0.284	0.283
AMARE _z [%]		\mathcal{T}_{ls} : 4.640		\mathcal{T}_x : 4.605		\mathcal{T}_{ls} : 15.884		\mathcal{T}_x : 14.685		\mathcal{T}_{ls} : 2.664		\mathcal{T}_x : 2.534		\mathcal{T}_{ls} : 10.657		\mathcal{T}_x : 8.074	

$$= 0, \quad (\text{A.3})$$

$$\frac{\partial \mathcal{L}}{\partial \Sigma_k} \Big|_{\hat{\Theta}} = \frac{\nu_{ls;k}}{2\Sigma_{x;k}} - \hat{\omega}_k^2 \frac{\nu_{x;k}}{2\Sigma_{x;k}^2} \begin{bmatrix} \hat{\theta}_{x;k} \\ 1 \end{bmatrix}' \bar{V}_k \begin{bmatrix} \hat{\theta}_{x;k} \\ 1 \end{bmatrix} = 0, \quad (\text{A.4})$$

$$\frac{\partial \mathcal{L}}{\partial \nu_k} \Big|_{\hat{\eta}} = \frac{\nu_{x;k} - \nu_{ls;k}}{2} \frac{\partial}{\partial \nu_k} \Psi \left(\frac{\nu_k}{2} \right) \Big|_{\nu_{x;k}} = 0, \quad (\text{A.5})$$

$$\frac{\partial \mathcal{L}}{\partial \eta} \Big|_{\hat{\eta}} = - \frac{\nu_{x;k}}{2\Sigma_{x;k}} \left(\hat{\omega}_k^2 \hat{\theta}'_{x;k} S' S \hat{\theta}_{x;k} + \hat{\omega}_k^2 - 1 \right) = 0. \quad (\text{A.6})$$

Since $\Sigma_{x;k} > 0$ (and $\nu_{x;k} > 2$), the prefactor in (A.6) is nonzero, and hence (A.6) implies $q'q = 1$, where $q \equiv [\hat{\omega}_k \hat{\theta}'_{x;k} S' \hat{\omega}_k]'$. Substituting this inner product into (A.3) yields $\Sigma_{x;k} = \hat{\eta}$. Moreover, since $\frac{\partial}{\partial \nu_k} \Psi \left(\frac{\nu_k}{2} \right) > 0$ for $\nu_k > 2$, (A.5) implies $\nu_{x;k} = \nu_{ls;k}$. Solving the stationarity condition (A.2) for $\hat{\theta}_{x;k}$ gives $\hat{\theta}_{x;k} = (V_{ls;k} - \hat{\eta} S' S)^{-1} V_{ls;k} \hat{\theta}_{ls;k}$. Exploiting the expression for $\hat{\theta}_{x;k}$ and performing straightforward algebraic manipulations, one can show that

$$\begin{bmatrix} \hat{\theta}_{x;k} \\ 1 \end{bmatrix}' \bar{V}_k \begin{bmatrix} \hat{\theta}_{x;k} \\ 1 \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} S \hat{\theta}_{x;k} \\ 1 \end{bmatrix}' \mathcal{Z} \begin{bmatrix} S \hat{\theta}_{x;k} \\ 1 \end{bmatrix}. \quad (\text{A.7})$$

After substituting (A.7) into (A.4) and using $q'q = 1$, the feasible values of $\hat{\eta}$ are generated by the Rayleigh quotient $\hat{\eta} = \frac{q' \mathcal{Z} q}{q' q}$ (Sec. 11.5 in [18]) and are therefore bounded between the smallest and largest eigenvalues of \mathcal{Z} . For the stationary feasible candidates, the objective satisfies $\mathcal{L}(\hat{\Theta}) = C + \frac{\nu_{ls;k}}{2} \ln \left(\frac{\Sigma_{x;k}}{\Sigma_{ls;k}} \right)$, where C is independent of $\Sigma_{x;k}$. Hence, using $\Sigma_{x;k} = \hat{\eta}$, minimizing \mathcal{L} amounts to selecting the smallest admissible value of $\hat{\eta} > 0$. By the Rayleigh-Ritz extremal property, the smallest admissible $\hat{\eta}$ equals the smallest eigenvalue of \mathcal{Z} , attained when q is the associated eigenvector. This choice thereby enforces global optimality of \mathcal{L} over the admissible domain.

To establish uniqueness of the global minimizer $\hat{\Theta}$, we examine the second-order sufficient conditions. As the Hessian is positive semidefinite, it remains to verify strict positivity of its quadratic form on the tangent space of feasible directions. Specifically, for every nonzero feasible direction β satisfying $\frac{\partial (\nu_k (\omega^2 \hat{\theta}'_{x;k} S' S \hat{\theta}_{x;k} + \omega^2 - 1))}{\partial \Theta} \Big|_{\hat{\Theta}} \beta = 0$ the condition $\beta' \frac{\partial^2 \mathcal{L}}{\partial \Theta \partial \Theta'} \Big|_{\hat{\Theta}} \beta \equiv Q(\beta) > 0$ must hold. The Hessian of \mathcal{L}

evaluated at $\hat{\Theta}$ and $\hat{\eta}$ is given by

$$\frac{\partial^2 \mathcal{L}}{\partial \Theta \partial \Theta'} \Big|_{\hat{\Theta}} = \begin{bmatrix} \mathcal{H}_{11} & O' \\ O & \begin{bmatrix} \frac{1}{2} \frac{\nu_{x;k}}{\Sigma_{x;k}^2} & -\frac{1}{2} \frac{1}{\Sigma_{x;k}} \\ -\frac{1}{2} \frac{1}{\Sigma_{x;k}} & \frac{1}{2} \frac{\partial}{\partial \nu_k} \Psi \left(\frac{\nu_k}{2} \right) \end{bmatrix} \Big|_{\nu_{x;k}} \end{bmatrix},$$

where the submatrix \mathcal{H}_{11} is of the form

$$\mathcal{H}_{11} = \begin{bmatrix} \underbrace{\frac{1}{2} D'_\theta (V_{x;k} \otimes V_{x;k}) D_\theta}_A & O & \underbrace{\hat{\omega}_k D'_\theta \text{vec}(V_{ls;k})}_b \\ O & \mathcal{H}_s & O \\ \hat{\omega}_k \text{vec}(V_{ls;k})' D_\theta & O & \hat{\theta}^2 \frac{2}{\hat{\omega}_k^2} \end{bmatrix},$$

with $\mathcal{H}_s = \hat{\omega}_k^2 \frac{\nu_{x;k}}{\Sigma_{x;k}} (V_{ls;k} - \hat{\eta} S' S)$. Let the vector $\beta = [\beta'_P, \beta'_\theta, \beta'_\omega, \beta'_\Sigma, \beta'_\nu]'$ be partitioned conformably with Θ . Then, the linearized constraint implies $\hat{\omega}_k^2 \hat{\theta}'_{x;k} S' S \beta_\theta + \beta_\omega / \hat{\omega}_k = 0$. For any feasible direction $\beta \neq 0$, the quadratic form associated with the Hessian admits the exact decomposition

$$\begin{aligned} Q(\beta) &= (\beta_P + A^{-1} b \beta_\omega)' A (\beta_P + A^{-1} b \beta_\omega) \\ &+ \hat{\omega}_k^2 \frac{\nu_{x;k}}{\Sigma_{x;k}} \beta'_\theta (V_{ls;k} - \hat{\eta} S' S) \beta_\theta + \frac{\nu_{x;k}}{2\Sigma_{x;k}^2} \left(\beta_\Sigma - \frac{\Sigma_{x;k}}{\nu_{x;k}} \beta_\nu \right)^2 \\ &+ \beta_\nu^2 \left[\frac{1}{2} \frac{\partial}{\partial \nu_k} \Psi \left(\frac{\nu_k}{2} \right) \Big|_{\nu_{x;k}} - \frac{1}{2\nu_{x;k}} \right]. \end{aligned} \quad (\text{A.8})$$

Since $A \succ 0$, $V_{ls;k} - \hat{\eta} S' S \succ 0$ by the Poincaré separation theorem (see Sec. 11.10 in [18]), and the bracketed term in (A.8) is strictly positive, each term in (A.8) is nonnegative, and the sum can vanish only if $\beta_\theta = 0$ and $\beta_\nu = 0$. The feasibility relation then yields $\beta_\omega = 0$, whereas the remaining two squared terms imply $\beta_P = 0$ and $\beta_\Sigma = 0$. Hence, $Q(\beta) = 0$ implies $\beta = 0$, or equivalently, $Q(\beta) > 0$ for every nonzero feasible direction β . Therefore, the second-order sufficient condition holds, and $\hat{\Theta}$ is the unique minimizer.

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